

1 Elements of the imprinting system can be modulated despite Xist core component stability.

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7 In this case, Baz2a, a major Xist RNP complex component functioning in autosomal Xist functions and
8 ATRX, a structural component that functions in Xst ncRNA localization in both developmental and
9 autosomal gene regulatory responsibilities of Xist were mobilized by the cellular perturbation or difference.
10 The data also bring to attention a growing and overlooked concept by which components of a system also
11 function as regulatory components of the system that support both activity dependent functions as well as
12 homeostatic resetting.

13 The data describe graded activation of a system with wide applicability across tissues and contexts,
14 demonstrating transient activation without global loss of homeostasis arising from the change. Retention
15 of sensor-like activities by responding to changes in activity and system mobilization status enables
16 integration of complex considerations including transcriptional homeostasis related to message number,
17 complex composition in stoichiometrically sensitive processes and involvement of a system in multiple
18 processes. Xist functions including sensing of homeostasis across the transcriptome in a broad,
19 autosomal system for regulation of gene expression to enforce homeostasis during normal adult life
20 across tissues likely possesses a graded nature whose temporal qualities (quantity, style and duration of
21 activation events) remain incompletely defined.
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